

TKD-19-051**Full-Annulus Aerothermal Characterization of High Speed Turbine Outlet Flows****Jon Urbieto**

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ITP Aero**ABSTRACT**

Conventional measurements of efficiency in low pressure turbine rigs are generally conducted by means of stationary temperature and pressure rakes, equally spaced around the annulus, at the inlet and outlet planes (a set of three rakes is usually employed for each variable). This approach is not adequate in high-speed multi-stage IP turbine rigs, however, on account of the wider variations in the local velocity vector whirl and radial angles found at the turbine outlet, caused by the use of highly-twisted outlet guide vanes (OGVs). Besides, there is also the possibility of circumferential non-uniformities arising from both tip clearance and leakage flows, as well as from inlet temperature variations, convected through successive turbine stages and which would increase the uncertainty of overall efficiency calculations if not considered. From an experimental standpoint, this leads to the requirement of conducting full-annulus circumferential aerothermal measurements of high spatial resolution.

This paper presents the development and commissioning of a new module for the acquisition of such measurements at the OGV outlet plane. The module consists of a rotating case instrumented with three pairs of pressure and temperature rakes (in addition to static pressure tapings on the walls and two Kulite arrays for the acquisition of noise measurements – which are not discussed here, however). The rakes traverse the OGV outlet plane as the module rotates, which allows for the full 360° characterization of the total pressure and temperature fields. The static and dynamic calibrations of the module sensors and rakes are described, and measurements acquired on a high speed turbine rig are presented.

Experiments were conducted in the transonic wind tunnel at the CTA (Spain), where turbine Mach and Reynolds numbers, and corrected speed are matched to engine conditions. The working section consists of a fully-featured three-stage turbine, including the final row of highly-twisted OGVs. The facility is comprehensively instrumented with stationary pressure and temperature rakes both at inlet and outlet, pressure tapping arrays on the vane surfaces, and an automated traversing system that is utilized with both hot wires and five-hole aerodynamic probes. Total pressure measurements conducted with the new module are shown to be in agreement with those of a five-hole probe, but they can be acquired up to 18 times faster. As opposed to employing three rakes at stationary circumferential positions, the total temperature maps presented here allow for a significant reduction in the uncertainty of thermal efficiency calculations.

INTRODUCTION

Outlet Guide Vanes (OGVs) usually generate significant circumferential variations of total pressure and temperature at their outlet plane (Hoeger et al., 2017). Besides, if they are placed close to the upstream rotor blades, OGVs can cause a circumferential redistribution of mass flow rate that can, in turn, lead the rotor to extract a different amount work depending on the circumferential position (Rojo, 2017). The use of highly-twisted outlet guide vanes, as is typically the case in Intermediate Pressure Turbines (IPTs), can increase this effect to a significant extent. Finally, it is worth noting that tangential non-uniformities in the flow field can also arise from inlet non-uniformities in the experimental facility. It is therefore essential to measure the full 360° degrees of total pressure and temperature when characterizing the overall thermodynamic efficiency of a complete turbine rig. With only three total temperature and pressure rake at the exit plane, as is conventional in low pressure turbine (LPT) rig tests, the uncertainty of efficiency measurements can be unacceptably high in the presence of non-negligible circumferential non-uniformities.

A new module for the acquisition of 360°-degree total pressure and temperature measurements have been developed and commissioned at the CTA, for use in the turbine transonic wind tunnel experimental facility (Vázquez et al., 2003). The module has been employed to measure the thermodynamic efficient of a complete 3-stage IPT turbine rig, including a final row of 12 highly twisted OGVs. This paper describes the new measurement module, its instrumentation, calibration and commissioning, and presents full annulus measurements of total pressure and temperature that demonstrate the accuracy and spatial resolution of the experimental technique.

NOMENCLATURE

CTA:	Centro Tecnologías Aeronáuticas
IPTs:	Intermediate Pressure Turbine
LPTs:	Low Pressure Turbines
KH:	Kiel Heads
OGV:	Outlet Guide Vane
UTR:	Universal Temperature Reference

ROTATING MODULE DESCRIPTION

Set Definition

The rotating module consists of two static casings and a rotating one. In order to assure, on the one hand, the rotating casing rotates concentric to the static ones and, on the other hand, they cannot separate axially, two customized bearings were manufactured.

One of these bearings has a cogwheel mounted to transmit the torque of the motor that controls the rotation. Between the engine and the cogwheel there is a gear and a planetary gearbox with which it is possible to have an adequate transmission ratio and a resolution of 2.70×10^{-4} degrees. To avoid leaks between the static parts and the rotating part of the module when rotating, two quad rings (one on each side) are installed and an adjustment procedure is performed during the assembly so that they work in their optimum working area. In the static casing at the output part of the module, a liner is installed in order to attenuate noise unwanted frequencies during aeroacoustics measurements.

Figure 1. Design model of the rotating module set.

Instrumentation Distribution and Wiring Routing

All the instrumentation in the module is mounted on strips to give versatility to the assembly.

For pressure measurements, there are three equally spaced (120°) strips for pressure rakes and static pressure tappings in the front casing and in the strips.

For temperature measurements, three equally spaced strips (120°) can be found for temperature rakes and static temperature tappings.

The rake strips have three different axial positions where the rake can be mounted in order to have the possibility to measure in different axial planes. Taking into account this distribution, only a 120° turn is necessary to measure the pressure and temperature map of a complete section. However, a 140° turn is usually performed to compare measurements from different rakes.

Each rake is mounted in the module by means of an actuator that consist of a stepper motor allowing to rotate the rake on its axis in order to place the kiel heads oriented to the flow remotely during the test.

In addition to the rake trips, there are two strips for probes separated 60° from each other where usually five holes fast response probes are mounted.

Finally, two strips with 168° between them are possible to be instrumented for Kulite pressure transducers to perform aeroacoustics measurements. Each strip covers all the axial length of the rotating casing so that 28 Kulite transducers can be mounted with a specific axial distribution for an optimum modal decomposition. Additionally to the two rotating arrays, it is possible to mount

five static Kulite transducers; two are placed at the entrance of the module, another two at the exit of the module, and one at the exit of the liner.

In addition to the instrumentation mentioned, four DSA bricks are mounted in the module to perform all pressure measurements so that delays in the response can be avoided.

There is an added difficulty related to the wiring routing. The instrumentation wiring has to turn with the module without causing damage to the instrumentation or itself. To avoid any damage, on the one hand, the more sensitive instrumentation, such as Kulite transducers, is protected with a methacrylate coverage and, on the other hand, the wiring is routed and tied to the casing until all the wires are put together in a mallet which is wound with the movement of the module in a specific section. In that section there is hardly any instrumentation.

Figure 2. Front view of the Instrumentation distribution.

Motion Control

In order to assure the module is not going to get out of the motion range required, two end of career switches are physically placed. Indeed, a homing switch is also needed to take the zero reference of the module position.

The module motion control is performed by a servomotor which has an encoder that it is measured in synchronization with the acquisition of the instrumentation data to know the instantaneous position of the module.

The sweeps are carried out automatically by means of a software where a table of movements is programmed including different speeds, stops and triggers. This control system is synchronized with the probes radial actuator system and the data acquisition system.

INSTRUMENTATION

Description

To perform the measurements at the OGV outlet plane, several types of instrumentations have been mounted in the rotating module. The instrumentation consists of three pressure rakes, three temperature rakes, static pressure tapings, wall temperature thermocouples and five-hole fast-response probes. Details of all measurements systems are given next:

Temperature acquisition system:

The thermocouples used are K-type, because of their higher frequency response. Thermocouples cold junctions are connected to a thermally insulated UTR, placed close to the calibration section to minimize the length of thermocouple wires. Voltages are measured using a VXI Pentium controller model E1401B, with 4 acquisition cards (HP E1419-012). The signal conditioner is an eight-channel low pass filter signal conditioning plug-on module, the model VT1509. The working temperature is kept at $23 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$, controlled by an air conditioner system in an isothermal room. A thorough calibration of both equipment and measurement procedure yields a final voltage uncertainty below $1 \mu\text{V}$. The UTRs are KeyInstruments, model X0290. Each UTR has a thermistor placed inside, manufactured by Fluke, Model 5611.

Pressure acquisition system:

- Differential bricks from Scanivalve, models DSA-3017/3018, have been employed. These are digital sensor arrays of temperature compensated piezoresistive differential pressure transducers, with full scales of both 5 and 15 psi.
- Three absolute pressure transducers, also from Scanivalve, model SPC3000, with respective full scale ranges of 23, 30, and 100 psi.

Five-hole probe pressure transducers:

- Endevco 8507C, piezoresistive.

Static Calibrations

Static calibrations of pressure measurement sensors have been performed both internally (at CTA or ITP Aero) and externally (outsourced), for traceability purposes. All dynamic calibrations were conducted prior to beginning the experimental campaign, in a representative range of operating test conditions in terms of Mach and Reynolds numbers.

For each kind of measurement calibration, one externally calibrated standard is needed: pressure measurements are calibrated with SPC3000 pressure calibrators, VXI analog to digital converter (bench temperatures measurement equipment) is calibrated by a Agilent digital multimeter 6.5 digit model E1412A, and the thermocouples used to efficiency measurements are calibrated in a bath using a precision thermometer for temperature measurement and a high accuracy voltmeter for thermocouples voltages.

The internal static calibrations consist of four main groups: Voltage (VXI channels), temperature (thermocouples for efficiency measurements) and pressure transducers (conventional and mounted in fast response probes).

- Conventional pressure transducers, (Differential bricks SCANIVALVE, models DSA-3017/3018. Range: 5psid, 15psid. These digital arrays of temperature compensated piezoresistive pressure transducers are calibrated in the whole range with a $\pm 0.05\%$ FS accuracy using SPC3000 pressure calibrators. For every brick (49off) and every channel (16off each brick) a full range calibration was performed, and a certificate generated.
- Endevco 8507C sensor for fast response five-hole probe are statically calibrated in its full range for different temperatures along the expected temperature at their measurement section in the rig. SPC3000 pressure calibrators and an oven to change temperature are used for this purpose. The calibration matrix for the sensors depends on the probe they are mounted in and the rig section this probe is going to measure at. For every temperature and transducer, 16 pressure points equi-spaced in the transducer range are used to calibrate the sensor and obtain a 3rd order calibration law to convert VDC to Pa. For each sensor is also measured the excitation current as this is the parameter used to assess the actual temperature of the transducer.
- Type K thermocouples are statically calibrated in a water/oil bath following the next procedure regarding water bath (cool ramps, -25 to 80 degC) and oil bath (hot ramps, from 60 to 200 degC), number of ramps and number of calibration points at each ramp. Following this procedure, two 6th order laws are calculated for every thermocouple, every coil and also for the batch, one to calculate degC from Volts and the other one to calculate Volts from degC.
- VXI analog to digital converter: A software is used to perform automatic calibrations of every analog to digital converter VXI card, the system generates and measures (by means of the E1412A card) zero and full-scale voltages for the different gains of the conditioners. An offset calibration is also performed for every channel.

Some of the external calibrations are:

Dynamic Calibrations

Traversing probes and rakes are also dynamically calibrated prior to the rig test campaign (or recalibrated in case of using existing ones), in a high-speed wind tunnel representative of test conditions, maintaining exactly the same measurement chain as in the test for pressure measurements and almost the same measurement chain for temperature measurements (only the UTR is different for calibrations and tests). The instrumentation set that is dynamically calibrated ahead of testing is composed of pressure and temperature rakes, five-hole probes and temperature probes.

The calibration process is carried out in the calibration tunnel placed at CTA (Pinilla, 2016). It is a closed-loop wind tunnel in which the Mach number can be varied up to 0.8. Also, the static pressure, and thus the Reynolds number, can be fixed independently with values ranging from atmospheric pressure to 10 kPa, approximately. The absolute humidity is reduced to avoid condensation in the calibration air jet, which is likely to happen for Mach numbers above 0.6. The main characteristics of the tunnel are:

- The working section is fitted with a circular contraction of 50mm exit diameter.
- The specimen to calibrate is placed with its tip at an axial distance from the exit plane of 25mm, that means, 0.5 diameters.
- The stagnation pressure is measured in the upstream plenum with a pitot tube.
- The static pressure is measured 0.20 meter away from the discharging nozzle.
- The inlet stagnation temperature is measured by a thermocouple placed in the upstream plenum chamber.
- The facility includes a robot arm to place the specimen on each point of the angle sweep and a data acquisition system.

Figure 3. View of the calibration facility with the probe installed.

Depending on the actual flow field conditions of the rig measurement planes, the calibrations are performed at different Mach numbers and static pressures to reproduce all the test conditions of interest along the full IPT turbine. Measurement instrumentation is also calibrated at different radial and whirl angles in order to confirm its sensitivity to flow alignment. In figure 4, rig test conditions are represented together with the calibration tunnel points of operation.

Figure 4. DP vs Radial

Five Hole Probes:

Five-hole probes are usually calibrated at two different static pressures: ambient pressure and one sub-ambient pressure representative of rig test conditions. For each pressure, they are calibrated for a Mach range depending on test conditions. For each Mach calibration point, yaw and pitch angles are varied from -60° to 60° resulting in around 2300 points per calibration run.

Pressure rakes:

These are usually calibrated only for one static pressure and one Mach number, mainly to check that each Kiel-head sensor in the rake is measuring properly. Each Kiel-head is calibrated varying yaw between $-/+35^\circ$ with pitch equal to null and vice versa.

Temperature rakes:

The total temperature measurement has a big impact in efficiency, so every probe of every rake is dynamically calibrated in the Reynolds/D and Mach conditions at which this probe is going to operate during tests. In figure 4 different inlet and exit conditions are shown for the rig working points as function of Re/D and Mach numbers. The figure also includes some of the possible operating points of the calibration tunnel. For each Mach number and static pressure, all Kiel-heads in the rakes are calibrated varying yaw between $-/+35^\circ$ with pitch equal to null and vice versa (as was the case for pressure rakes).

Considering all the data from the calibrations performed for the rakes and temperature probes, a standard Recovery Factor as a function of Re/L is assumed to correct the total temperature measurements during the test campaign.

Figure 5. RF vs Re/D. Inlet and exit rakes have been averaged.

MEASUREMENT PROCEDURE DESCRIPTION

Measurements in the outlet plane of the IPT turbine rig have been acquired by means of pressure and temperature rakes, which rotate with the rotating measurement module. There are 3 pressure rakes and 3 temperature rakes attached to the rotating measurement module, equally and alternately spaced. This allows a complete measurement of the outlet plane to be performed by a 120° rotation of the rotating module (in practice, however, a total of 140° is rotated to have two 10° overlap windows at the interfaces between a rake and its successive). This type of measurement is called a bullet. Fast-response probes and temperature probes can also be attached to the rotating module to acquire measurements of flow angles during its traversing motion.

The bullet measurement procedure, mainly dependent on its angular velocity, was characterized ahead of conducting actual measurements in the turbine rig. The optimum angular velocity is affected by two opposite requirements. First, very slow angular velocities (or even stopping traverses) would be desirable because they allow enough time to stabilize the flow around the sensors. This prevents the acquisition of transient experimental measurements if, for instance, the stabilization time is lower than the response time of the data acquisition system. However, very slow traverses of the measurement plane may be affected by global drifts in the facility operating conditions, the characteristic time of which can be hours (similar to the temporal interval of slow or stopping traverses).

The optimum angular velocity of bullet measurements was determined both for measurements with rakes and with fast probes. In the case of the rakes, tests were made at 5 angular velocities of the rotating module: 56 %/min, 71 %/min, 95 %/min, 120 %/min and 140 %/min. Turbine efficiency was calculated with each of these measurements and compared with the efficiency obtained using a stopping traverse at the turbine outlet plane. For each angular velocity of the rotating module, three pairs of back and

forth passes were made and measurements have been averaged, first, on each round trip and, second, between the three passes at each angular velocity.

The analysis of results is summarized in **TABLE 1**, which shows a comparison of differences in efficiency and specific work between bullet angular velocity tests and measurements acquired in stopping traverses. Total traverse durations are also indicated in the table. The analysis was conducted on two different test days. Full annulus measurements have been mass-averaged. Two conclusions were reached. First, the efficiency measurements based on the five angular speeds of the rotating module coincide with each other with a precision of $\pm 0.013\%$, for a 95% confidence interval. This is approximately an order of magnitude lower than the overall uncertainty of efficiency measurements in the facility (which is around $\pm 0.1\%$). On the basis of this study, therefore, it is possible to neglect the effects of angular velocity variations on the efficiency calculations. Furthermore, comparing the efficiency calculated with the average of all angular velocities for a given test day with that of the stopping traverse, the difference is upper bound by 0.01% for tests on day 1, and by 0.03%, slightly higher, for tests on day 2. In both cases, the variations are lower than the overall uncertainty of the efficiency measurement technique. With respect to a stopping traverse, the bullet measurement time can be reduced by a factor of 8 to 20, depending on the angular velocity.

Difference in variable	Test day	Stopping traverse	56 %/min	71 %/min	95 %/min	120 %/min	140 %/min
$\Delta\eta$	1	Benchmark	-0.004%	0.003%	0.000%	-0.005%	-0.013%
	2	Benchmark	0.026%	0.027%	0.020%	0.024%	-
ΔW_{sp} (%)	1	Benchmark	-0.022%	-0.003%	0.009%	0.013%	0.010%
	2	Benchmark	0.029%	0.080%	0.103%	0.042%	-
<i>Time (min)</i>	-	40	5	4	3	2.5	2

Table 1: Summary of differences in efficiency and specific work measured in bullet angular velocity tests with respect to a stopping traverse

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experimental measurements of total pressure (left) and total temperature (right) acquired in the aerodynamic design point of an intermediate pressure turbine by the bullet technique are presented in **jError! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..** The presence of whirls generated at the trailing edge plane of the OGVs can be clearly observed in both figures (there are 12 OGVs in the full row). Whirls downstream of the OGV outlet plane are approximately centered at mid-span, which is precisely where the OGV pressure and suction surfaces are swapped due to its high level of twist. The fact that the interfaces between measurements of each rake and its two adjacent ones are virtually non-observable lends confidence to the measurement technique and experimental results. The mixing and redistribution of low momentum areas in the flow field can be appreciated in the figure, such as the fact that loss cores migrate from the casing towards the center of the passage but remain much more constrained on the hub region. Although the flow is, on average, nominally axial downstream of the OGVs, there are regions of both slight overturning and underturning due to the trailing edge vortices.

It is worth considering how the overall efficiency obtained from the full annulus measurements compares to that which would have been obtained by just 3 rakes on stationary positions. For this analysis, the usual circumferential positions of pressure and temperature rakes have been taken, namely, 20.45° , 150.45° and 280.45° for the pressure rakes, and 0.46° , 130.46° and 260.46° for the temperature ones. The efficiency based on full annulus measurements was 0.25% higher, a difference that is larger than the experimental uncertainty of the technique. Thus, employing the rotating measurement module allows for the acquisition of thermodynamic efficiency measurements of both high accuracy and high spatial resolution.

Figure 6. Full annulus measurements of total pressure, in kPa (left), and total temperature, in K (right), acquired at the aerodynamic design point in an intermediate pressure turbine

CONCLUSIONS

A new rotating module has been developed and commissioned in the transonic wind tunnel at the CTA. This rotating module has been designed to allow for different type of instrumentation such as rakes and probes. As the module rotates, and the rakes and probes with it, there is a full 360° characterization of the total pressure and temperature at the turbine outlet plane. This feature allows for a reduction on efficiency uncertainty for turbine rigs, which has been estimated to be around 0.25% for a complete turbine rig with highly twisted OGV. Moreover, due to the careful design of the measurement chain, test time for single conditions has not increased significantly. It has been proven that with only two minutes a full 360° outlet characterization is obtained without penalizing the efficiency measurement.

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